

EMPLOYING REDUPLICATION IN THE DIALECT OF YUSUFZAI PASHTO LANGUAGE VIA MORPHOLOGICAL DOUBLING THEORY

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Abstract

This research highlights the use of Reduplication in the dialect of Yusufzai language which is an indo -Iranian language spoken not only in some areas of Pakistan but also Afghanistan. Pashto language has undergone through various phases of evolvement. Thus, it was the central focused of many research studies that uncovered its several prominent features and the researcher does not need to unearth its every hidden aspect. Consequently, the researcher aims to examine the total, partial and non-sensical Reduplication in the dialect of Yusufzai language. The collected data has been conducted from the native speakers from informal settings which has been confirmed by the experts such as / Zar Zar / means quickly (Total reduplication). Pohantun -Mohantun means university (partial Reduplication). Karrat Karrat means nonsense (non-sensical reduplication). The analysis of the data clearly manifested that Yusufzai language is widely spoken in various regions of Pakistan such as, Buner, Swat, Malakand, Sawabi, Mardan, Batgram, Mansehra, and Haripur. The Yusufzai language is rich employing Reduplication in the daily conversation of those areas.

Keywords: *Partial Reduplication, Reduplication, Total Reduplication, Yusufzai dialect, Yusufzai Pashto language*

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1. Introduction

Pashto is an official language of Afghanistan which is spoken not only in Afghanistan but in Pakistan as well (Sadiq & Bibi, 2022). Afghanistan acknowledges the Pashto language as a national language and the common language for the purpose of speaking (Omari & Asadi, 2022). Pakistan also acknowledges numerous languages in terms of speaking. Therefore, it is a diverse country of multilingualism (Rasool et al., 2023). In terms of speaking, most of the other languages for instance, Pashto, Balochi, Sindhi and Punjabi are practised at the level of provinces (Sadiq et al., 2021). Among them, Urdu is an official language practised nationally. Every language has similarities with the sound and structures to the other language but they have distinctions with several number of sounds and various word-formation structures and processes. So to speak, it has been noticed that every language has different structures to its vocabulary in opposite to another language (Ali & Ilyas, 2020).

Several researchers have tried to work on multiple local languages of Pakistan including, Urdu, Pashto, Saraiki, Punjabi, Sindhi and Balochi recognised paramount languages of Pakistan. However, numerous local languages of Pakistan are considered at the minor or secondary level, and many researchers do not research on those languages so there is a dire need to study and explore those local languages and their beauty (Sadiq et al., 2021).

The Pashtun greatest tribe is Yusufzai that establishes the most of the landowning nobility in Malakand, Swabi, Buner, Swat, Shangla, Mardan, Torghar, Dir (both upper and lower) regions, and other villages such as, Batgram, Mansehra, and Haripur districts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. This tribe is widely known for its civilization, tradition, history, power and linguistic supremacy. The dialect of Yusufzai Pashto language is acknowledged as a second large and standard variety of Pashto language (Dinakhel, 2020). Furthermore, Pashto has also gained the prominence of the official language of Swat state declared by the ruler of Swat named Miangul Abdul Wadud from 1915 to 1969 (Dinakhel & Ali, 2012).

Pashto is a native language of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa which is predominantly spoken in its regions. The native-speakers of this language are called Pakhtoons. The study of Pashto language has been less prioritized and explored from the research point of view. Moreover, it has been split into two major dialects. One is Qandahari which is generally known as Khattak dialect or Southern dialect. It is practised especially in the areas of Pakhtunkhwa and Pakhtoons prevalent areas of Balochistan where Pashto is widely practiced such as, Quetta, Pishin, Zhob, Loralai and Killa AbdSadiq, and the second one is Yusufzai dialect and some historians named it Peshawari dialect which is widely practiced and spoken in Pakhtunkhwa such as Mardan, Swat, Malakand and Dir on account of socio-cultural and economic influences. The distinctions can be seen phonetically in the

dialects by the sounds of [kh] and [Sh], and some differences in the vowel use (Garcia & Munir, 2016).

Numerous facet of discerning dialects phonologically, phonetically, syntactically, lexically, morphologically, semantically and so forth. There is one more technical term, accent, that keeps the corresponding association with the term dialect. Mostly dialect is different lexically and syntactically while accent varies different changes phonologically and phonetically (Boberg et al., 2018). It is essential to know the distinctions among different dialects mentioned in this article.

When the script and patterns of the Pashto language is observed, it clarifies that it has been evolved through several stages. In the beginning, it opted for a number of modern forms “from other linguistic systems” (Gracia & Munir, 2016). The employment of reduplication can be seen in the dialects of Yusufzai Pashto language.

Montaut (2009) stated that reduplication is identified at the syntactic level in South Asian areas. Both the written and the spoken scripts are discovered in every walk of life. As per Kauffman (2015) and Rubino (2001), reduplication has two major kinds, for instance, full and partial. Rubino (2001) manifests that total reduplication encompasses the repetition of the entire word, word stem with the help of affixes or root, and partial reduplication is in different form; consonant and vowel lengthening, simple, complex, and automatic. Therefore, the researcher investigates on the dialects of Yusufzai language employing the total, partial and nonsensical reduplication. This study currently Spheres on this phenomenon to find out what type of reduplication is present in the Yusufzai language.

The twofold ways of repeating a word have been explored by the researchers and writers such as inflection and derivation. When there finds no change in the main word and it inserts the intensity to the grammatical meaning, is called inflectional reduplication, on the other hand, the derivational reduplications bring changes in meaning and category of the base word (Ambarita, 2018).

Every language has remarkable rules which are being followed around the world that distinguish a language to perform various functions in terms of syntactic, semantic, morphological and phonetic. (Ramzan et al., 2023). Moreover, Reduplication can take several forms in terms of words, phrases and sentences which can be referred to lexical, phrasal and syntactic reduplication (Hurch, 2005). It has been examined full reduplication is often employed in several languages as to illustrate, English, Urdu, Sindhi, Punjabi, Saraiki, Balochi, Pashto and many others (Ramzan et al., 2023). with this, Linguists are interested in exploring the hidden qualities of a language, and in recent years, it has been noted that the production of duplication and reduplication has been a topic of interest for linguistics experts (Hurch, 2005).

1.1. Research Questions

- What kinds of reduplication exist in the dialect of Yusufzai Pashto language?

- What functions do reduplication perform in the Yusufzai Pashto language?

Research Objectives

- To investigate the kinds of reduplication in the dialect of Yusufzai Pashto language.
- To examine the functions of reduplication in the Yusufzai Pashto language.

1.2. Significance of the study

The significance of the study anticipates to have applicable effects on the research on indigenous languages and unofficial languages which are off the record. It provides a reasonable contribution to the research to conceiving the morphological traits of the Yusufzai dialect of Pashto and it also aims to explore an unexplored area in the dialect of Pashto language to the future researcher.

1.3. Delimitation of the study

In this current time, this study focuses on only the dialect of Pashto Yusufzai language rather than other dialect of Pashto language. For this study, specifically native speakers are selected from Swat, Buner, Malakand, Swabi, Shangla, Mardan, Torghar, Dir (both upper and lower) regions, and other villages such as, Batgram, Mansehra, and Haripur. There is no any another dialect used like Qandahari which is spoken in various areas of Quetta.

2. Literature review

Diverse aspects of syntax have been examined during the study of reduplication (Ramzan et al., 2023). These studies cover the context of foreign language (Abdelrady and Akram, 2022; Akram and Abdelrady, 2023), as well as the second language (Ramazan et al., 2023). Raimy (2000) examined both the morphology and phonology layers. On the contrary, Zuraw (2002) paid attention to analyzing purely phonological aspects of reduplication, particularly Tagalog, a language spoken in the Philippines.

Morphological doubling theory (MDT) illustrates how words can have two parts that mean the same. This theoretical framework was proposed by Inkelas and Zoll in 2005, the initial ideas were found from Singh (1982), Saperstein (1997), Sherrard (2001), and others. In Morphological doubling theory (MDT), This doubling is more concerned with meaning rather than pronunciation. The process applies to entire words, stems or roots. Unlike improving the sound of words when combined, which aims how they are heard. It, the morphological doubling, deals with grammar based rules for creating words. This principle allows repeated use of word parts for its meaning, not its sound.

Researchers have studied reduplication in numerous languages utilized either morphological or phonological strategies. The approach helps explain how reduplication works different linguistics systems. In this study, two main theories are commonly used: Base Reduplicant Correspondence Theory (BRCT) proposed by McCarthy and Prince (1995), this theory focuses on phonological aspects of language, and a theory called

Morphological Doubling Theory (MDT) coined by Inkelas and Zoll (2005), focuses of the repetition of word parts with the same meaning. MDT helps understand how reduplicated word parts carry meaning rather than just sound. These theories provide a structure for assessing reduplication across different languages.

As per Kouwenberg (2011), it is fascinating to observe that reduplication does not only limit to fully acquired languages but also detected in pidgins and creoles. Masahiko (2011) provides a detailed study of this process in TokPisins, separating reduplication from repetition and defining it as a morphological process. Findings indicate that reduplication in TokPisins is less productive than repetition, with full reduplications occurring more often than partial ones.

Leroy and Morgenstern (2005) reported that numerous experts study child language by investigating reduplication in the accumulation established upon children's conversations. In addition to, research on reduplication is related to grammar that is the focal point in diverse languages, such as, pidgins and creoles, such patterns also operate alongside semantic and pragmatic purposes.

In addition to, the vast and great studies are performed on reduplication in multiple languages in all over the world, but it is viewed that exclusive studies have been conducted on the word formation process in Pakistan. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, there is no research has been carried out so far in the context of Karachi. Therefore, the researcher explores the total, partial and nonsensical reduplication in the dialect of Yusufzai Pashto language.

3. Methodology

The collection of data has been gathered for this study from the native speakers of Yusufzai language who are the inhabitants of Buner, Swabi, Swat and Mardan. Moreover, the real setting such as public domain and friendship domain has been chosen for the data. The selected words which the researcher has chosen for the study have been discussed with the experts of Yusufzai language and the experts have confirmed that these words have the accurate meaning according to their functions. In terms of grammatical category, Nouns, Verbs, Adjectives and adverbs are categorized and analyzed by the researcher.

3.1. Data analysis

There are many examples of reduplication in the Yusufzai language in which the researcher has potentially and painstakingly analyzed the data which has been collected from the native speakers of Yusufzai language. therefore, Inkelas (2008) advocated the Framework of the dual theory which has been used for the analysis of data. To use different kinds of Reduplication in Yusufzai language which is repeatedly used in their dialogues and conversation by highlighting the data which has been analyzed.

Total Reduplication which carries the repeated word which is attached to the base word called full Reduplication whereas the partial Reduplication carries changes

phonologically occurring in the base word (Khanjan & Alinezhad, 2010). On the other hand, In the process of total reduplication, the whole root word is repeated while the partial brings changes in the base word vowel and consonantly (Rubino, 2005). In addition to, the nonsensical reduplication occurs when repeating a word or part of the word which does not develop meaning or logic productively but it is repeated humorously to create the funniest effect (Nawaz et al., 2024).

3.2. Total Reduplication

Pashto Duplication **English Translation** **Grammatical Aspects**

Khabara Khabara	Talk	Noun
Zar Zar	Quickly	Adverb
Pas Pas	whisper	verb
Khwashala Khwashala	Happily	Adverb
Shum Shum	Miser	Noun
Rupai Rupai	Money	Noun
Jara Jara	Weeping	Noun
Spiny Spiny	Truth	Noun
Tar Tar	Destroyed	Adjective
Drun Drun	Heavy	Adjective
Kha Kha	Fine	Adjective
Bangri Bangri	Spoiled	Adjective

- Zar Zar Raza
- Come quickly
- Khwashala khwashala Raza
- Come happily

Total reduplication is the process of repeating words in which the prior part of the word is duplicated alike. The word “**Zar Zar**” which has been shown in the data is a compound word and it comprises of two morphemes such as “**Zar**” is the first part which functions as an adverb and it means “**quickly**”.while the second part is the repetition of the first part which cannot transform its grammatical aspect and remains same that is why it is called Reduplication.in addition to, the purpose of employing the another word which is attached to the first part is for intensity and emphasis in communication and dialogues.

Furthermore, the word which the researcher uses such as, “**Khwashala Khwashala**” mentioned in the above table. This word is a compound word which consists of two morphemes for instance, “**Khwashala**” which is the first part that functions as an

adverb and it provides the proper meaning of this word “**happily**”. In order to describe another part of this word, which may not move its grammatical facet and it remains duplicate. Therefore, another word which the researcher has utilized with the first part demonstrates stress and accentuation in written and oral communication.

The word “**Bangri Bangri**” is a total reduplication which carries two morphemes functioning as an adjective which develops the meaning of this word “**Spoiled**”. The first part of the word that can create meaning but the another part cannot transfer its grammatical aspect and it remains constant.

3.3. Partial Reduplication

Pashto Duplication	English Translation	Grammatical Aspects
Pohantun Mohantun	University	Noun
Naas Pas	Sit	Verb
Sapera Mapera	Slap	Verb
Dodai Modai	Bread	Noun
Che May	Tea	Noun
Masta Wasta	Yoghurt	Noun
Waraa Maraa	Children	Noun
Ubo Mubo	Water	Noun
Shomle Momle	Buttermilk	Noun
Chargh Mergh	Chicken	Noun
Unghwale Munghwale	Curry	Noun
Wrax Mraz	Day	Noun
Shpaa Ma	Night	Noun
Agai Magai	Egg	Noun

- Ayaa taso Pohantun Mohantun ta Zai ?
- Do you go to university?
- Zaba darlaa sapera mapere darkam.
- I will slap you.

Some parts of the words in partial Reduplication which is the kind of reduplication are repeated or geminated in the process. The example of partial Reduplication which is aforesaid in the table, “**Pohantun-Mohantun**” is a compound word and it functions as a noun that means a “**University**”. Moreover, this consists of two morphemes “**Pohantun-Mohantun**” in which the first part of the word “**Pohantun**” provides the complete meaning to understand. On the other hand, the second part “**Mohantun**” which does not

have any complete semantic meaning but it carries differences phonologically in the base form.

Moreover, the researcher takes another word “**Sapera Mapere**” from the table mentioned above which is the partial reduplication. The word “**Sapera**” is a compound word functioning as a verb which provides meaning of the word as “**Slap**”. It is the compound word which has two morphemes like “**Sapera Mapere**” in which the first part of the word “**Sapera**” gives the entire meaning to comprehend. On the contrary, the another part which is “**Mapere**” which does not provide the entire semantic meaning but it creates distinctions on the basis of phonology in the base form.

3.4. Nonsensical words in Full and Partial Reduplication

Pashto Duplication	English Translation	Grammatical Aspects
Duze Duze	Boast	Verb
Tur Tur	Speak nonsense	Verb
Karrat Karrat	Nonsense	Noun / Adjective
Kat Kat	Flattery	Noun
Karr Karr	Rough rattling sound	Noun
Gharr Gharr	Rumbling	Adjective
Par Par	Flap	Verb
Chaq Chuq	Creaking	Noun
Tes Tapas	Chaos	Noun
Garr Barr	Disorder	Noun
Tas Tos	Quarrel	Verb / Noun
Kundi Kapare	Bumpy	Adjective
Akhwa Dikhwa	Misguide	Verb
Angrra Dangrra	Excuse	Noun / Verb
Karrate Pate	Fight	Verb
Spera Sosarr	Unlucky	Adjective
Agate Bagati	Nonsense	Noun

- Mara Duze Duze ma waya.
- Do not boast.

A repeating word or a part of the word in a way is involved that does not provide meaning or sense is called Nonsensical reduplication. The word which is taken from the above table is “**Duze Duze**” is a compound word used in Pashto language which has two morphemes functioning as a verb but it does not have any sense. Therefore, the researcher

explores the nonsensical reduplication in Pashto language in terms of making it easier for other researchers.

3.5. Mara sta tole khabare asy agate bagati de.

Your all words are nonsense.

The word which is taken from the table “**Agate Bagati**” is partial nonsensical reduplication and it carries two morphemes functioning as a noun. The word “**Agate Bagati**” is a partial nonsensical duplication as the first part is “**Agate**” and the second part “**Bagati**” is not repeated and it is different from the first part. Moreover, this word does not provide meaning or logic but it is utilized in a language

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, Reduplication which brings changes in meaning by germinating or repeating the base or the part of the base word. The study is limited to the Reduplication of Pashto. The main focused is on full and partial Reduplication in this study. Two types of Reduplication in the Yusufzai language have been found and analyzed with their contextual utilization are defined. The analysis of the data demonstrates intelligibly that Yusufzai language is exceptionally rich in relation to bring changes of reduplication i.e. full and partial reduplication in the dialect of Yusufzai language.

6. Recommendations for Further Research

The researcher has explored full, partial and nonsensical Reduplication which is only limited to the dialect of Yusufzai language and this data has been collected from native speakers of this language. Moreover, this study will facilitate other researchers who will work on a research on the dialect of Yusufzai language to explore non sensical Reduplication for the development in Indo -Iranian language. As a matter of fact, the use of Reduplication in indigenous languages is explored and used in Pakistan as it is found in Yusufzai language.

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